

Voltammetric trace level determination of sulfide in presence of sulfite and thiosulfate

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Abstract : A voltammetric study of sulfide ion has concluded in developing of a simple method of its determination at low concentrations. Sulfite and thiosulfate did not interfere. The limit of quantification was achieved 2.2 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ by using differential pulse polarography. The method has successfully been applied for the analysis of sulfide contents in waste samples.

Keywords : Sulfide, DPP, industrial wastes, trace determination.

Introduction

Sulfur and its compounds are widely used in industries of paper, pulp, tanneries and textile. These subsequently produce a large number of anionic forms such as sulfide (S^{2-}), sulfite (SO_3^{2-}), sulfate (SO_4^{2-}), thiosulfate ($\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$) and tetrathionate ($\text{S}_4\text{O}_6^{2-}$). Sulfide is rather more concerned species because of its toxic nature¹. Therefore, it is appropriate to develop a simple analytical method for the determination of sulfide. Voltammetric methods have proved more useful in such studies as these can identify and determine ionic forms of a species due to the certain selectivity of the redox potential². We had earlier reported the voltammetric determination methods for nitrite and nitrate³, bromide and chloride⁴, chlorate⁵ and iodate elsewhere⁶. Herein, a study of sulfide ion in polarographic media of 0.1 M sodium chloride in 0.1 M nitric acid shows the possibility of developing a voltammetric method for the determination of sulfide at low concentrations.

The electrochemical data on sulfide has indicated that the polarographic behaviour of sulfide was first investigated by Kolthoff and Miller⁷ in acidic and alkaline medium. Canterford and Buchanan⁸ have shown anodic electrode processes of halides and sulfide at the surface of the dropping mercury electrode by using pulse polarography. The square-wave polarographic determination of

sulfide in water is given by Redinha *et al.*⁹. Renard *et al.*¹⁰ have determined sulfur compounds including sulfide in liquors by ac polarography. Ensafi *et al.*¹¹ have carried out cyclic voltammetry and linear sweep voltammetry in study and determination of sulfur anions with a glassy carbon working electrode. The authors have envisaged the suitability of differential pulse polarographic (DPP) method which has enabled the determination of sulfide in presence of its associated major sulfur species i.e. sulfite and thiosulfate without any interference. The DPP results also compares favourably with the UV-Vis spectrophotometric technique.

Results and discussion

Electrochemical behaviour of sulfide : Choice of medium.

In preliminary investigations different supporting electrolytes such as sodium chloride, nitric acid, hydrochloric acid, acetic acid and ascorbic acid were studied to observe electrochemical characteristics of sulfide ion at the dropping electrode. An amount of 0.1 M sodium chloride in 0.1 M nitric acid was found to be most adequate medium where sulfide showed a polarographic wave at -0.18 V vs SCE. The half-wave potential of the wave ($E_{1/2}$) seemed to be pH dependent, however, at pH 1.2 the wave appeared well-defined and diffusion controlled. The plot of E vs $\log i/(i_d - i)$ revealed that electrode reaction was not fully reversible in nature.

DPP studies :

The optimized analytical conditions were found for the low concentration determination of sulfide by differential pulse polarography. In the presence of 0.1 M sodium chloride in 0.1 M nitric acid sulfide gave a sharp DP peak at -0.18 V. The linearity of the peak current and the concentration of sulfide was obtained in the range of 2.2 to 8.0 ppm. The calibration curve characteristics were as follows : slope, 0.08; coefficient of correlation (*r*), 0.99; intercept, 0.11 and standard deviation, ±0.95. It has been drawn in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. The calibration plot of sulfide in 0.1 M NaCl - 0.1 M HNO₃ (pH 1.2).

Interference :

Sulfite and thiosulfate, the major coexisting sulfur species with sulfide were monitored during the DPP determination of sulfide in industrial wastes. The peak potential of SO₃²⁻ in these conditions was noticed at -0.3 V, which is well-separated from that of S²⁻ at -0.18 V. Similarly, S₂O₃²⁻ showed a DP peak at -0.08 V, illustrating no interference. Peak potential of sulfur species are listed in Table 1. The interference studies cum observations are shown in Fig. 2.

Limit of determination :

The limit of determination of sulfide was found to be 2.2 μg/ml.

Table 1. Peak potential of sulfur species in 0.1 M NaCl - 0.1 M HNO₃

Sr. no.	Sulfur species	- E _p (V) vs SCE
1.	S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻	0.08
2.	S ²⁻	0.18
3.	SO ₃ ²⁻	0.33

Fig. 2. DPP of S²⁻ (5 × 10⁻⁴ M) in presence of SO₃²⁻ and S₂O₃²⁻ (5 × 10⁻⁴ M, each) in 0.1 M NaCl - 0.1 M HNO₃ (pH 1.2) : Modulation amplitude, 50 mV; pulse duration, 57 ms; clock time of pulse, 1 s and scan rate, 12 mV/s.

Analytical applications :

The devised optimum conditions in terms of polarographic medium, calibration linearity and detection limit, were applied to analyse sulfide contents in spiked industrial waste samples.

Voltammetric measurements :

A measured volume of the prepared sample was taken into the polarographic cell with 0.1 M NaCl in 0.1 M HNO₃ (pH 1.2). DP polarograms were recorded from 0.0 to -0.5 V and peak currents were noted at -0.18 V after making the blank correction. The concentrations were determined by the standard addition method¹². The results of determination of sulfide are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. DPP determination of sulfide in industrial waste samples

Sample ^a	S ²⁻ (ppm)		
	DPP ± SD	RSD (%)	Relative error (%)
Paint industry (3.95)	3.91 ± 0.03	0.76	1.01
Alloys industry (5.0)	4.49 ± 0.01	0.22	0.20
Metal industry (6.0)	5.91 ± 0.04	0.67	1.50

n = no. of determinations; 3.

Values shown in parentheses is sulfide (ppm) spiked in industrial waste samples.

^aWaste samples were collected from Basni Industrial Area in Jodhpur.

Validation :

The validity of the measurements has been demonstrated by comparing the results of DPP with UV-Vis spectrophotometric method. The data so obtained are compared in Table 3.

Table 3. Comparison of results of determination of sulfide by DPP and UV-Vis spectrophotometry

Sample	UV-Vis (ppm)	DPP (ppm)
1.	3.90	3.91
2.	4.44	4.49
3.	5.90	5.91

Sample 1, 2, 3 from paint, alloys and metal industry.

Thus, the results of sulfide determination by present method are in good agreement with other techniques including differential pulse polarography as reported by Canterford and Buckanan⁸ in terms of detection limit ($1 \times 10^{-7} M$).

Conclusion :

The DPP method for the determination of sulfide is of simple approach, rapid and specific. Furthermore, the peak potential of S²⁻ in presence of 0.1 M NaCl in 0.1 M HNO₃ was obtained at -0.18 V. It was therefore more convenient for measurements without interference of sulfite and thiosulfate. The method will be useful in research and industrial laboratories where sulfur compounds are employed for multiple uses.

Experimental

Instrumentation :

A microprocessor based pulse polarographic analyzer (Model CL-362) in combination with a drop timer assembly, all of Elico Limited, Hyderabad, India, was used for

voltammetric measurements. Voltammograms were recorded by an Epson printer (Model LX-300+II). The instrumental settings for DPP were as follows : a dropping mercury electrode was used as the working electrode; pulse amplitude, 50 mV; pulse duration, 57 ms; clock time of pulse, 1 s and scan rate 12 mV/s. Potentials were measured against a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) and a platinum wire acted as an auxiliary electrode throughout.

A UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Model SL-160) of Elico was also used for sample analysis. It has a wavelength range from 190–1100 nm. A tungsten halogen deuterium lamp and wide range photomultiplier were used as the light source and detector, respectively. The spectral band width of resolution was 0.5 nm.

Keeping in view the fact that the iodometric method suffers interference from reducing substances that reacts with iodine, including sulfite and thiosulfate, the methylene blue method was employed for analysis of sulfide where absorbance of the species was measured at 664 nm¹³.

The pH measurements were made by a digital pH meter (Model-5000) of Lab India.

Sample collection and treatment :

Industrial waste water samples were collected in clean polyethylene containers. These were filtered in order to separate any suspended particulate matter. A 100 ml aliquot of sample was treated with 1 ml of an oxidizing mixture of nitric acid and sulfuric acid to destroy the biological and organic matters. The pH of the treated sample was maintained ≈2 for analysis¹⁴. A known concentration of sulfide was added and it was taken as the test sample. Test solutions were deaerated for 20 min by passing nitrogen. It was purified by bubbling through a vanadous chloride scrubbing solution¹⁵. Chemicals used were of analytical grade. Stock solution of sulfide was prepared from sodium sulfide. All experiments were carried out at ± 298 K.

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